

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fLOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 7.4

COLLABORATION WITH COVENANT OF MAYORS AND EXTERNAL COMMUNITIES

Due date of deliverable: 31/05/2022

Actual submission date: 31/05/2022

Start date of project: 01/06/2019 Duration (36 Months)

Dissemination Level: Public

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.*

DELIVERABLE

Work Package	WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation & Sustainability
Deliverable	D7.4 Collaboration with Covenant of Mayors and External Communities report
Task(s)	Task 7.3 Liaisons with Covenant of Mayors and Target Audiences [M1-M36]
Document Name	Collaboration with Covenant of Mayors and External Communities report
Due Date	M36: 31 May 2022
Submission Date	M36: 31 May 2022
Dissemination Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> P – Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO – Confidential
Deliverable Lead	Copenhagen Business School (CBS)
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Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This report presents the results of WP 7, Task 7.3 Liaisons with Covenant of Mayors and Target Audiences within the REFLOW project. It describes how the project as a whole and the individual pilot cities have interacted with the target audiences of the project, including the Covenant of Mayors, to raise awareness about the results, and collect feedback and validation on the solutions developed.
Keywords	Dissemination; Feedback; Validation; Target Audience; Covenant of Mayors
Statement of Originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author(s)	Organization	Description
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D7.4 v0.1	13 January 2022	Veronica Chesi	CBS	<i>Table of Content</i>
D7.4 v0.2	08 April 2022	Dina Bekkevold Lingås, Anna Schmid, Andrea Frøshaug	CBS	<i>First draft</i>
D7.4 v0.3	14 May 2022	Marcel Pîrvu, Manon Taillebois	Cluj-Napoca Municipality, FAB CITY GRAND PARIS	<i>Change by partners</i>
D7.4 v1.0	20 May 2022	Dina Bekkevold Lingås	CBS	<i>Final version by the consortium to be submitted to the EC.</i>

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Abbreviations

A&E Tracker	Action and Event Tracker
CBS	Copenhagen Business School
CE	Circular Economy
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
EMEA region	Europe, Middle East, Africa Region
EPC	European Policy Center
EU	European Union
IFG	Industrial Focus Group
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
NCH	Nordic Case House
PCP	Pre-Commercial Agreement
RCGT	Regenerative Collaborative Governance Toolkit
Relfow OS	Reflow Operating System

SME	Small-and Medium Sized Enterprise
STIR	Start-Up In-Residence Program
WP	Work Packages

Glossary

Dissemination	Dissemination of the developed solutions
Material Passport	A cryptographically signed trace of all the events a material resource has gone through (a resource's history), including actors and other processes, events & resources present in those events
Makers	Builders, Inventors, Manufacturers, Constructors etc.
Output	All measurable results from the project, or simply put, everything that the Reflow project has achieved. Includes time-limited results such as events, and long-term changes such as a new sorting system for the retailer in Vejle.
Pilot	A small-scale test or experiment in the preparation for bigger activities at a later stage
Pilot city	The six pilot cities of the Reflow project: Amsterdam, Vejle, Berlin, Paris and Milan.
Project -Level Reflow Resources	All resources which support and enable the innovative solutions of pilot cities, such as tools, methodologies, and framework
Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit (RCGT)	A resource conceived to support the design and development of collaborative governance arrangements for the transition to circular and regenerative cities. This consists in a how-to practical guide for cities based on the REFLOW Framework to enable new forms of infrastructuring collaboration in ways that can unleash distributed agency and capacity for innovation
Reflow Framework	A design thinking Framework developed during the Project to facilitate a whole system change towards circularity. See more in D.1.3
Reflow OS	Operating System based on GNU/Linux distribution technologies helping to incentivise circular practices in local ecosystems by monitoring and optimising urban metabolic processes. Peer-to-peer network to conduct economic activities such as monitoring, track and trace, and coordination among participants
Solution	An output from the Reflow project which offers a new way of tackling a circularity challenge. Not all outputs are solutions, some are for instance events or publications.
The Reflow Platform	The REFLOW Platform refers to all the project-level resources in REFLOW that support and enable the development, prototyping and implementation of innovative solutions in the pilot cities. The resources are not limited to those developed in REFLOW, i.e., the platform incorporates tools, resources and methodologies that were both created by project members or selected by them from existing frameworks and deployed in the project to support the development of pilot solutions

Valueflows	A set of common vocabularies to describe flows of economic resources of all kinds within distributed economic ecosystems. It is based on the REA (Resource, Event, Agent) economic model
Value Chain	The concept describing the full chain of a business's activities in the creation of a product or service

Consortium Members

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15	MCS DATALABS	MCS	Germany
16	COMUNE DI MILANO	MILAN	Italy
17	WEMAKE S.R.L.	WMK	Italy
18	OPENDOT SRL	OD	Italy
19	FAB CITY GRAND PARIS	FCGP	France
20	COMMUNE DE PARIS	PARIS	France
21	ARS LONGA	ARSL	France
22	VOLUMES	VOL	France

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26	FILIALA TRANSILVANIA A ASOCIATIEI ROMANE PENTRU INDUSTRIA ELECTRONICA SI DE SOFTWARE	ARIES	Romania
27	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU TEHNOLOGII IZOTOPICE SI MOLECULARE-INCDTIM CLUJ-NAPOCA	ITIM	Romania
28	BERLIN WASSERBETRIEBE	BWB	Germany

1 Introduction

1.1 About Reflow

Reflow is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, Reflow uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualize and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximize multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project will provide best practices aligning market and government needs to create favourable conditions for the public and private sector to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. Reflow is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle and assess their social, environmental, and economic impact, by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

1.2 Reflow Vision

A circular and regenerative city in Reflow represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to **social, environmental, and economic impact**; where **technology** is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and support resilience of social and ecological systems; where **governance** is collaborative and inclusive; where **knowledge** is shared, and **stakeholders** are active and involved.

1.3 About the deliverable

The Reflow project is based on the understanding that the transition to circular and regenerative practices in cities requires a redesign of the local ecosystem to create favourable conditions for both public and private sector to adopt CE practices. Cities must work across sectors to provide a more holistic interpretation, allowing a systematic view of problems and objectives of what urban life should be like. A key basis for the work of Reflow has therefore been to involve a range of local, national, and European stakeholders in the development of the outputs. Their involvement has contributed to solutions that are realistic for public, market and government needs, and that can be scaled and replicated in other cities. In other words, an important success criterion has been to ensure that the solutions have not been developed in isolation. Although these aspects have been present in the work of all partners, pilots, and work packages, WP7 has had a particular responsibility to ensure the projects connection and collaboration with all relevant external stakeholders. More specifically, a key part of the overall objective of this WP has been to maximise the impact of the project's results through i) *Communication and dissemination activities at EU and local level for which involves a range of stakeholders*, and ii) *Establish and engage external stakeholders in the validation and, evaluation and wider use of project's results*.

More specifically, this deliverable reports on the work associated with Task 7.3: Liaisons with Covenant of Mayors and Target Audiences.

The objective of this task has been to support the pilots and work packages in establishing and maintaining continuous interactions with the Covenant of Mayors in particular, policy making institutions / agencies at EU and national level in general, and the range of target audiences identified by Reflow. See explanation of these below:

1. **The Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy:** Is an initiative that brings together local and regional authorities who voluntarily commit to implementing the EU's climate and energy objectives on their territory.
2. **Target audiences:** The choice of target audiences has been made based on the stakeholders identified as key by Reflow as a whole. These include policy making institutions/agencies at EU and National level, SMEs and Start-ups, citizen's associations, CE professionals, companies and institutions, researchers, scientists, and individuals interested in CE, from the enlarged-Europe and beyond.

The goal of the interactions has been to ensure co-creation of the results with relevant stakeholders, gather external feedback to fine-tune the results, and obtain validation of the final solutions.

Definition of the project's results: When referring to the project's results, this report includes both Reflow Pilot Solutions and Project Level Solutions. The Pilot Solutions refer to the solutions most developed and innovative. The Project Level solutions refer to resources built upon a collaboration between WPs and pilot cities, which are not connected to a specific material flow or pilot city.

The reader should keep in mind that the different pilot cities have developed different types of solutions and followed different strategies in the development of the solutions and have consequently focused on different target audiences. This has in turn resulted in different ways as well as amount of external interaction. Therefore, the number of different target audiences each solution has interacted with, is not indicative of the pilot city efforts, nor the quality of the interaction and thus the obtained feedback, validation, and dissemination.

Through this, the task has contributed to the dissemination of the project's results and to create synergies with the relevant linked initiatives. Seeing as interaction with externals has been done extensively throughout the project, on a small and big scale, this report does not aim to document every interaction (reported in D7.3 Communication and Dissemination Activities Report), but rather provide an overview of the most important for the development of the solutions. More about how this deliverable connects with other deliverables, can be read in Ch. 1.6.

Method: As a deliverable reporting on the work and actions of the pilots and work packages throughout the project, the deliverable builds upon documentation provided in previous deliverables and project resources. More specifically, information taken from the A&E tracker, D1.2 and D1.3 outlining the pilot action plans, D1.4 describing the different pilot and project level resources, D1.5 and the description of KPIs where these have involved external interaction.

In addition, the pilots have contributed with their analysis of the *effect* of these interactions on the development of their solutions, and this deliverable hence combines the various data on activities carried out through the project and shows how the combination of many small and big activities and interactions have been important for the feedback, validation and dissemination of the project's results.

1.4 Structure of the report

The deliverable is made up of three main parts: 1) The interaction with Covenant of Mayors and policy makers and policy making institutions, 2) The Feedback, Validation, and dissemination of project level solutions, 3) Feedback, Validation and dissemination of pilot solutions.

Each chapter have a set of sections and sub-sections, as described below:

- 1) **Liaisons with The Covenant of Mayors and Policy Makers:** This chapter describes the general connection between Reflow and the Covenant of Mayors specifically, and policy making institutions specifically.
 - a. Reflow and the Covenant of Mayors.
 - b. Reflow, policy making institutions and city networks, both from a project and pilot level.
- 2) **Feedback, Validation, and Dissemination of project level resources:** The chapter focuses on the most developed and comprehensive tools, methods and frameworks from the Reflow Platform, and presents how both internal and external stakeholders have been involved in the development. Although the feedback from other consortium partners is not considered completely external, it still provided valuable input as it was given from another organisation from another field and with a different expertise. A summary of this feedback is therefore included in this deliverable. It is divided into four sections, one per project level solution. Included within each section are the following sub-sections:
 - a. Description of the solution
 - b. Internal feedback
 - c. External feedback, validation, and dissemination
- 3) **Feedback, Validation, and Dissemination of the Pilot cities with target audience:** This chapter describes how the pilots have engaged with external stakeholders in the development of their outputs. The chapter does not cover all outputs but focusses on those with the most external interaction. The chapter is divided into six sections, one per pilot city. Included within each pilot section are the following sub-sections:
 - a. Pilot introduction
 - b. Local contribution: the work and input to the local transition to circular and regenerative cities both about circular economy in general, and material/topic specific for their pilot. Of the two-way interaction, this part refers to how the pilots have provided knowledge, inspiration, engagement to their local context, as opposed to receiving feedback and validation on their own specific solutions.
 - c. Feedback: feedback on their solutions, presented by solution. Including stakeholder, specific topic for the feedback, type of feedback, and effect on their solution
 - d. Validation: both validation of specific solutions, and the pilot's work overall. This part is somewhat intertwined with the local contribution, in the sense that the extensive opportunity that all pilots have had to be a voice in their local context on the transition to circularity, can also be understood as a validation of the relevance of their work.

1.5 Connection with the Reflow Framework and other deliverables

The overarching objective of this deliverable is to show how the solutions of Reflow have benefitted from external interaction, feedback and validation throughout the development. This is not related to any specific point in the process or level of the Reflow Framework but is rather cross-cutting and relevant for the iterative process between the different levels. That said, external interaction is crucial to take the solutions to scaling beyond the pilots, which places it on a meso level.

Figure 1. The Reflow Framework. Source CBS

Looking at this report’s connection to other deliverables, there are several other tasks and deliverables which also touches upon co-creation and dissemination.

First, the importance placed on external feedback and validation is also reflected in Task 7.5 – CE Adoption Industrial Focus Group, through which the consortium has engaged external experts to gather feedback and validation of both pilot solutions and project level solutions. This task does not have a dedicated deliverable, and as the aim of T7.5 can be seen as overlapping with T7.3, the work done in the former will also be included in this deliverable.

Second, D7.3 – Communication and Dissemination Activities Report which reports on the dissemination activities at large, based on an internal database, the Action & Event Tracker, where relevant events during the project lifetime have been registered in a quantitative manner. Many of the same activities are reported in this deliverable, however here they are presented in a qualitative manner, to describe in more detail how the activities have contributed to the development of the project’s results. Additionally, the quantitative overview of dissemination of the project signifies a proxy for validation of the project as a whole. Reversely, the qualitative interactions with the aim to gather feedback and validation, contributes to awareness spreading about the project and thus the dissemination of its results. However, pure dissemination activities are not included in this deliverable.

Third, this deliverable is strongly connected to D5.5 – Citizen engagement and Capacity Building. Citizens are a key target audience for Reflow, and as such, this group has been an important group to get feedback and validation from. However, where D5.5. describes how the pilots have planned and organized their involvement of citizens, and reports on best practices for how to involve and engage citizens, this deliverable focuses more on the other direction of the interaction, namely how citizens have contributed to the development of the project solutions.

Fourth, the activities described in this deliverable, and particularly those through which the pilots have contributed to the local context, are connected to D6.2 – Community of Practice. The presentations, events, workshops, etc., which have been open for external participation have contributed to local, decentralized communities of practice around the specific topics and circular economy in general.

Fifth, the feedback and validation of the pilot solutions as described in this deliverable, connects closely with the business models developed, which are reported on in D7.5. A crucial part of business modelling is the testing with the target audience / market. This is not reported on in D7.5, and as such, this deliverable contributes to giving a more holistic and fuller overview of the work of the pilots on their solutions.

Last, the full description of the different project level solutions can be found in other deliverables:

- 1) The Reflow Operating System: D5.4 REFLOW Pilot Applications
- 2) The Reflow Academy: D6.3 Capacity Building Toolkit, D6.4 Multi-Platform Digital Resources and Structured Learning Courses, and D6.5 Collaborative Case Studies for Higher Education Curricula
- 3) Ecosystem Design: D3.3 Urban Metabolism Strategy Report

2 Liaisons with The Covenant of Mayors and Policy Makers

Reflow's mission is to understand and demonstrate how the reconfiguration of the urban metabolism can enable the transition to circular and regenerative cities. This has been done through the development of solutions within six pilot cities, each focussing on one specific city resource, as a way to understand, define, develop and release critical examples of how cities in general can adopt a circular economy model. Consequently, keeping in mind the replicability and scalability of the solutions has been a constant throughout the project. To ensure that the solutions, methods and models developed are indeed useful for other cities in Europe, the project has sought to keep close contact with existing city networks within the field of sustainability and circularity and policy making institution/agencies both on the local, national, and regional level, to both get feedback on the solutions and to disseminate and provide input to these bodies. Recognising the importance of public policy in the transition to circular and regenerative cities, a second objective of the project has also been to develop a set of policy proposals and guidelines on governance transition towards flexible urbanism (see D4.5).

In this chapter, the interaction with the city network Covenant of Mayors in particular, and city networks and policy making institutions / agencies in general will be described and evaluated. The chapter rounds-up with reflections on the feasibility of such interactions for Reflow as an Innovation Action.

2.1 Reflow and Covenant of Mayors

The Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy brings together local and regional authorities who voluntarily commit to implementing the EU's climate and energy objectives on their territory. The initiative started in 2008 with the support of the European Commission, and now counts over 10,948 signatories in 54 countries representing more than 338 million citizens. Since 2015, signatories pledge to reduce CO2 emissions by at least 40% by 2030 and to adopt an integrated approach to tackling mitigation and adaptation to climate change¹. The Covenant of Mayors is guided by the following vision:

¹ Covenant of Mayors. (2022). *Euro Cities*. Retrieved from covenant of Mayors: <https://eurocities.eu/projects/covenant-of-mayors/>

"Our vision is that, by 2050, we will all be living in decarbonised and resilient cities with access to affordable, secure and sustainable energy. As part of the Covenant of Mayors - Europe movement, we will continue to (1) reduce greenhouse gas emissions on our territory, (2) increase resilience and prepare for the adverse impacts of climate change, and (3) tackle energy poverty as one key action to ensure a just transition."

Out of the six pilot cities, five were already signatories of the Covenant of Mayors: Amsterdam, Berlin, Milan, Paris, and Cluj-Napoca. In Vejle, there has been a focus on the network Resilience 100 Cities, and it was not deemed relevant to also become a signatory of the Covenant of Mayors during the timeline of Reflow.

Reflow has sought to establish a dialogue with the aim of gathering feedback on both project and pilot level solutions, and to disseminate the results and learnings with other cities.

On a project level, the Covenant of Mayors Coordination and Management team was asked about the possibility for Covenant of Mayors to join Reflow's Advisory Board at the beginning of the project. This was unfortunately not feasible due to lack of internal capacity, but the possibility of Covenant of Mayors to promote information that could be relevant to the decarbonisation and resilience of the Signatories of the Covenant was welcomed. For this, a blog post describing how Reflow is working to enable the transition to circularity and regenerative cities was published on the Covenant of Mayors website. More specifically, the blogpost described the overarching concepts of Reflow, and how the Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit and the Reflow OS can support municipalities².

The internal team of Covenant of Mayors was also asked to contribute with feedback on the Reflow Collaborative Toolkit through an anonymous survey developed to gather feedback from external experts. Covenant of Mayors was invited due to their extensive experience with the work of municipalities and thereby a general knowledge of how municipalities work and their common challenges. The organisation was also invited to provide feedback on the Reflow OS.

Lastly, the Covenant of Mayors was invited to contribute to the Reflow Final Event, *the Circular Cities Conference: Reflow & Beyond*, as moderator of the session on *Policy: A Balancing Act in Strength and Diplomacy*. They were unfortunately not available to participate but shared the event on their online agenda.

On a pilot level, the work on liaising with Covenant of Mayors was mainly relevant in the last year of the project. Prior to this, the pilot solutions were not deemed developed enough to be presented and receive feedback on their potential for replicability and scalability on a European level. Once the necessary level was attained in the last year of the project, the Covenant of Mayors was approached. The primary goal was to get in contact with signatories from other cities than the pilot cities, through the Covenant of Mayors. Unfortunately, the Covenant of Mayors did not have the mandate to facilitate the connection. Therefore, the Covenant of Mayors itself was asked to give direct feedback on the usefulness of the different solutions for other EU cities, given their extensive experience with the work, possibilities and barriers of municipalities in Europe. Allegedly, the department focused on capacity-building activities shared the description of the solutions to their *taskforce*. However, no feedback or assessment was received.

Further, five blogposts focusing on each of the signatory pilots and their work with specific material flows was published at the [Library section of the Covenant of Mayors website](#), serving as inspiration for other cities. The cases covered the following solutions/topics: Amsterdam - the Denim Deal an alliance of international frontrunners; Cluj-Napoca - an immediate shift towards resource efficiency, Milan - digitalization as an enabler of

² Covenant of Mayors. (2021). *Reflow seeks to help your city transition to circularity*. Retrieved from Covenant of Mayors: <https://www.covenantofmayors.eu/news-and-events/news/1879-reflow-seeks-to-help-your-city-transition-to-circularity.html>

circular food markets in an urban, Paris – RE-Label, a local certification of circularity, and Berlin – Revealing an untapped resource context. The cases were presented at the *news section* of the Covenant of Mayors website.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the news section on the CoM website

Reflections

The Covenant of Mayors was identified as a particularly significant city network to liaise with at the beginning of the Reflow Project, due to its number of signatory European cities and focus on decarbonised and resilient cities, which resonates with the vision of Reflow. Although dialogue was established, there has been challenges related to realising the potential of obtaining feedback on pilot and project level solutions. This might be due to several causes, from either side, of which some might be worthy to take into consideration by the European Commission and other projects.

Firstly, the pilots and the work packages developing project level solutions, all expressed the need for more local co-creation particularly in the first two years of the project. Interacting with other cities and city networks was deemed premature. Consequently, the more focused attempts of liaising with the Covenant of Mayors happened at a later stage of the project with less time remaining to ensure in-depth and extensive feedback. Ideally, the input of other cities on the scalability and replicability of the solutions should be integrated from the very beginning of understanding a problem, defining, and developing the solution. However, the pilots experienced the need to limit the available feedback and range of input in the beginning to avoid being overwhelmed.

Secondly, the Covenant of Mayors had limited availability and mandate to connect the pilot cities with relevant other signatories. Further, the Covenant of Mayors expressed limited specialised knowledge and competence necessary to provide direct feedback on the solutions developed. In combination, this resulted in challenges leveraging the potential for Covenant of Mayors to be a valuable city network.

Lastly, the vision and focus of the Covenant of Mayors, being specifically about decarbonisation, mitigation and adaptation to climate change, and sustainable energy consumption, did in hindsight not perfectly reflect the focus of all the pilot cities. Out of the pilots, only two have been working on these topics specifically, namely Berlin (wastewater heat) and Cluj-Napoca (Energy efficiency). This might have limited the perceived relevance of the

Covenant of Mayors by the pilot cities, and / or affected the possibility of the Covenant of Mayors to provide in-depth and specific feedback to the solutions.

Despite the relative challenges in engaging extensively with the Covenant of Mayors, the pilots have been active in their interactions with policy making institutions and city networks in general, which is elaborated on in the next sub-chapter.

2.2 Reflow, policy making institutions and city networks

The Reflow Project has had close and recurring contact with policy making institutions at both European and national level, as well as with international city networks. These interactions have both happened on a general project level, and through the individual pilot cities. Naturally, the interactions on a general level have been more towards international institutions, organisations, and networks, whereas the pilot level interactions have been more on the national level, highly driven by the municipal partner of each pilot.

2.2.1 Project Level Interactions:

The Reflow Project has been actively involved with EU level and national policy making institutions, and city networks.

- **EU Industry Days:** The project was invited to contribute with a digital “booth” at the EU Industry Days 2022. This event is Europe’s flagship annual event, highlighting industrial frontrunners and ongoing industrial policy discussions whilst improving the knowledge base of European industry, and is the main platform to discuss industry challenges and co-develop opportunities and policy responses in an inclusive dialogue with a wide range of stakeholders³.
- **Project Meeting:** During the Consortium Project Meeting in January 2022 in Paris, the deputy mayor in charge of innovation and attractiveness of Paris mayor spoke about the impact of the Reflow project on the circular development of the city.
- **Final event:** At the final event of Reflow, *the Circular Cities Conference: Reflow & Beyond*, several policy makers and city networks were represented. The final event took shape as a conference over two days. The overarching aim of the conference was to share the results of the project and insights about key methodologies used in Reflow, as well as to contribute to the public discussion on circularity in cities. More specifically, the conference first explored the role of different stakeholders in the transition to circularity. Second, it presented the solutions developed in Reflow both on work package and pilot level, and provided a space for a discussion on how the solutions can be scaled to a national and European level. Lastly, the conference sought to explore how the next generations of actors and projects will embark on their circular transitions, and how the learnings from Reflow can be brought further. The first day of the conference was held as a webinar through the video platform “zoom”, whereas the second day was held in-person at Copenhagen Business School. Representatives from various public institutions, organisations and city networks participated as moderators and panellist at the different sessions. Other organisations were also part of the sessions but are not included in this overview as they do not represent policy makers or city networks. The full overview of the event can be found at the Reflow website⁴.

³ European Commission. (2022). *EU Industry Days*. Retrieved from EU Commission: <https://eu-industry-days.ec.europa.eu/>

⁴ Reflow. (2022). *Reflow Events*. Retrieved from Reflow: <https://reflowproject.eu/events/>

- *Governance*: Emanuela De Menna, Project Advisor at Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME), European Commission, moderated the session, where Marieke van Doorninck, Deputy Mayor for Spatial Development and Sustainability in the Municipality of Amsterdam and Dr. Antonia Gravagnuolo, Researcher, H2020 CLIC and Be.CULTOUR Project Coordinator at National Research Council, Italy were panellists.
- *Business*: Charlotte Gjedde, Head of Partnerships at State of Green Denmark contributed to the session as panellist.
- *Materials in the Circular City*: In this session, all six pilots had individual sessions in parallel, and included external stakeholders to discuss the replicability and scalability of their solutions. Relevant stakeholders for this deliverable were Robert Brandt, Managing Director of the German Renewable Energy Agency (Wastewater Heat).
- *Social Impact Assessment*: In this session, the project coordinator of Reflow presented the project's work with the topic and more specifically the Social Impact Assessment. The discussion was broadened by the participation of Steffen Kallehauge, Head of Impact at B Corp Movement in the Nordics.
- *Beyond Reflow*: In this session, the topic was how the work and results of Reflow can be scaled and transferred after the end of the project. Through this, the work was discussed with panellists Pernille Kernel, Special consultant on Circular Economy at the Centre of Regional Development, Capital Region of Denmark, and Agnese Boccalon, Project Manager at ACR+ – Association of Cities and Regions for sustainable Resource Management, representing the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative.

2.2.2 Pilot Level Interactions

2.2.2.1 Amsterdam Pilot

The Amsterdam pilot has had a close collaboration with the municipality and the metropole region of Amsterdam. For instance, the Amsterdam Economic Board and the municipality organized meetups, targeting circular textile. The meetings were designed as working session and progress meetings to discuss the development and process of the roadmap, in collaboration with 32 municipalities within the metropole region of Amsterdam. The outcome was the development of a policy document with a shared vision and mission, aligned amongst all municipalities, called the Roadmap on Circular Textiles. The connection with the municipality is also evident in the feedback and validation of a range of the solutions developed by the pilot.

2.2.2.2 Cluj-Napoca Pilot

The pilot has been actively involved in the drafting of the Integrated Urban Development Strategy 2030. The pilot considers the integration of sustainability and circularity principles into the Integrated Urban Development Strategy 2030 functions as an important long-term bottom-up approach to finding affordable innovative solutions for citizens, SMEs, other actors to become more energy efficient. In addition, the pilot has presented the concept of circular economy for approximately 25 mayors in Romania, ensuring that the Reflow project contributes to the agenda and public discourse outside of the specific solutions developed by the project.

2.2.2.3 Paris Pilot

The Paris pilot has been in dialogue with the Cultural Affairs Department since the launch of the Reflow project. The Cultural Affairs Department has participated in two brainstorm meetings with the Paris pilot on the needs of the cultural and creative sector. The contribution of the Reflow Paris pilot was solidified when the Department's working group on circular economy decided to take the Reflow project in the Paris pilot into account. As a result, the Paris pilot took part in the new national group on sustainable scenography, and came into contact with Paris Musées, who manage museums in the City of Paris.

2.2.2.4 Vejle Pilot

The Vejle Pilot has been closely connected with local politicians throughout the project. Public stakeholders include the Danish Environmental Protection Agency, the Innovation and Entrepreneurship and Waste and Environmental departments of the Municipality of Vejle, as well as Sofiegården – an elderly care centre. Moreover, the local politicians have been involved in the project – both in a local steering group committee as well as the supportive political committee KNMU (Climate, Nature and Environment Committee). The pilot has also been working in alignment with the city's Resilience Strategy through its connection with the municipality, which is involved within the 100 Resilience Cities initiative. Further, the pilot has engaged with public institutions and the procurement department in Vejle, giving 10+ procurement policy recommendations for healthcare institutions, based on the experience with waste management at the elderly home Sofiegården, input from WP4 and local stakeholders.

2.2.2.5 Berlin Pilot

While the Berlin municipality itself is not a formal part of the project, the Berlin pilot members have connected with the city at various occasions. For one, city representatives have been involved in the project in referring contact partners or giving input on data availability. Second, a relationship to CityLAB Berlin has been established. The CityLAB describes itself as a "public experimental laboratory for the city of the future; here, representatives from government, civil society, academia and start-ups collaboratively develop new ideas for how to both ensure and enhance the liveability of Berlin as a city". The Berlin Pilot and CityLab have collaborated in the areas of dissemination and exploitation.

2.2.2.6 Milan Pilot

As an active member in the C40 City Group, Milan provides a dynamic setting for the exploration and implementation of interventions for transitioning towards a circular and regenerative city. The Municipality of Milan has built upon and continues to advance a collection of policies and initiatives, that underpin and foster innovation in food-related matters by bringing together novel constellations of actors, spanning from a variety of institutions and expertise in the both the public and private spheres.

3 Feedback, Validation, and Dissemination of project level solutions

This section presents the feedback, validation and dissemination of the solutions developed on a project level.

The project level solutions are part of *the Reflow Platform*. The Reflow Platform is defined in D1.4 - Validation and Performance Evaluation as *all project-level Reflow resources* and includes **all** resources which support and enable the innovative solutions of pilot cities, such as tools, methodologies, and framework. A part of these resources are the solutions that have been developed by the WPs specifically within Reflow, and which are part of the assets with exploitation potential outside of the Reflow Project.

Most Project Level Solutions have received both internal and external feedback and validation. Internally, all solutions have received feedback from pilots and some also from other WPs through the ideation, development and after testing. As part of D1.4, the pilot cities evaluated the usefulness of the solutions for their work and what impact they have had on the development of pilot solutions through a survey and interviews. This feedback can be read in D1.4, Chapter 3. Some solutions have also received feedback from other project partners and WP's either formally or informally, or both. Lastly, some solutions have gotten external feedback and validation from organisations and stakeholders outside of the Reflow Consortium.

The Project Level Solutions:

- 1) Reflow Operating System
- 2) Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit
- 3) Reflow Academy
- 4) Ecosystem design

The section is organised as follows: For each project level solution, there is first a description of the solution, summarised from D1.4; then the internal feedback is described when relevant. Next the external feedback and validation is presented; and lastly the dissemination is briefly laid out. The reader should be aware that there are differences between the solutions regarding the extent and type of both internal and external validation, due to the significantly varying types of solutions.

3.1 The Reflow Operating System

3.1.1 Description

Reflow OS is an operating system for circular cities. The Reflow OS is an Operating System based on GNU/Linux distribution technologies that help to incentivize circular practices in local ecosystems by monitoring and optimizing urban metabolic processes. The Reflow OS offers a secure, peer-to-peer network that allows economic activities to be conducted, such as monitoring, track and tracing, and coordination among participants online without central control. Concretely, Reflow OS will allow the tracking and tracing of materials, observation of economic activities in real time, and enable a material marketplace. Reflow OS enables stakeholders to record data manually or automatically on the material flows they want to track at a custom level of detail. It further allows interested stakeholders to trace back the entire material flow at any time and observe any changes and updates of the data in real time. Users will be able to customize data visualization charts according to the metrics they want to highlight and monitor. The development of a ledger will allow for the safe storage and update of data of available materials exchanged (for free, with tokens, or with other materials) between stakeholders.

3.1.2 Internal feedback

The Reflow OS has been developed in close collaboration with the pilot cities on an ongoing basis during the project. This has happened on several levels:

1. Feedback on architecture and user friendliness has been given as the pilots have worked on implementing their solutions into the system. This work has been done both directly between the pilots and WP2, and through the pilot coordination work of WP5.
2. Feedback on the features have been given based on the process of business modelling in WP7, which showed the usefulness of different features based on business potential. For instance, based on that several business models are utilising an online platform for matchmaking between many units, it became apparent that the platform, and thereby the Reflow OS, should enable automatic matchmaking. Further, the BM process validated the benefit of the RF OS allowing users to choose which information is shared. For instance, the suppliers of data to the wastewater heat radar require anonymity, which is less feasible with pure blockchain technology.

3.1.3 External feedback, validation, and dissemination

The Reflow OS is based on components that are based on open consumption (GNU/Linux) distribution technologies and the sustainability of the adopted technology is guaranteed by the inclusion of the open-source code in GitHub, the largest online development platform, where it is shared to be further improved by other developers. Most of the components are already developed to a Technological Readiness Level of 6 and standardised by recognised bodies, whereas some of the components are based on pre-normative standards which are still emerging at different levels. Because of the principle of open source, the code has been available for the developer community at large, and consequently received feedback throughout the project at GitHub, as seen in the below image.

Figure 3: Screenshot of feedback throughout the project at GitHub

Further, WP2 and the responsible for the technological development in the Pilot cities, have been actively involved in discussions with the industry, and more specifically the creators of the Value Flow ontology, on how to implement Value Flows in Reflow OS. The below image shows an example of problem solving at the GitHub platform, where one of the original creators of the Value Flow ontology (“fosterlynn”) responds to an issue with the track & trace of the circular isolation gowns developed by the Amsterdam Pilot. More examples of such interactions can be found at GitHub⁵.

Open PrimaryAccountable of resource with specific id is not updated after a transfer event #3
ocataco opened this issue on Sep 13, 2021 · 14 comments

Update:

- * I have tried to pass the "atLocation" field with the id of the receiver to the "transfer" event, but the resulti
- * I have tried to create an extra "move" event (copying the parameters of the "transfer" action, thus providing toRe

The documentation of EconomicEvent.atLocation states: "The place where an economic event occurs. Usually mappable." So from the description this is not the right field to specify where it needs to update, but it seems to be the only field available to specify a location in the EconomicEvent.

fosterlynn commented on Nov 18, 2021

The documentation of EconomicEvent.atLocation states: "The place where an economic event occurs. Usually mappable." So from the description this is not the right field to specify where it needs to update, but it seems to be the only field available to specify a location in the EconomicEvent.

You are right, it is not the right field, but we "hacked" it in to use for updating resource location in `move` events, when we tightened up what resource properties can be modified by an update, and what can't be without an event. It doesn't really conflict for `move` we think, since `move` is internal to an agent, and tends to be close by, otherwise there would probably be a transportation process. But VF would be happy to fix that hack whenever the timing works for people. (We've been really careful about changes during this period of active software development, especially changes that might have some ripple effects, even just a lot of discussion time when people are busy with more important issues, and changes that are not particularly backwards compatible. But we only need to be as careful as you all want us to be.)

Also possibly relevant, the question came up should transfers also be able to update the location at the `toResourceInventoriedAs`. We don't think they need it. If there is a new resource created as a result of the transfer, `currentLocation` can be set at that time. If the transfer increments an existing resource, it probably already has its `currentLocation` if the agent cares about location.

adam-burns commented on Nov 18, 2021

Thanks Lynn, @ocataco does `currentLocation` usage work for you?

Figure 4: Screenshot of problem solving at the GitHub platform

There is also significant external validation of the Reflow OS as a whole and the individual components. Firstly, the external validation of some of the components of Reflow OS can be seen through the integration of these on other platforms and in other projects.

Reflow OS is being adapted as a core technical pillar of the INTERFACER project⁶. This is a project funded by the REACT-EU programme of the European Commission's NextGenerationEU plan, a programme to foster crisis repair and integrate the green and digital transitions into the recovery strategy to increase the resilience of the economy. Based in the Hamburg region, the Interfacier project aims to promote and further develop tools to

⁵ Github. (2021). *Dyne/ Reflow OS*. Retrieved from Github: <https://github.com/dyne/reflow-os/issues/3>

⁶ Fabcity Hamburg. (2022). *Interface*. Retrieved from Fabcity Hamburg: <https://www.fabcity.hamburg/fab-city-os-projekt-interfacier/>

enable collaborative circular economic activities across design and manufacturing activities and their supply chains, especially for local FabLabs and regional SMEs.

Leading on from cryptographic innovations and implementations stemming from the Reflow graph signature scheme, Dyne has partnered in a consortium for a successful pre-commercial procurement (PCP) tender bid for the European Commission initiative "EBSI" and is awarded to build a prototype of the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI) that also includes an evolving Digital Product Passport pilot.

3.2 Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit

3.2.1 Description

The Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit (RCGT) is a resource conceived to support the design and development of collaborative governance arrangements for the transition to circular and regenerative cities. This consists in a how-to practical guide for cities based on the Reflow Framework to enable new forms of infrastructuring collaboration in ways that can unleash distributed agency and capacity for innovation. The toolkit is conceived as an evolving process based on a timeline, ranging from local to national, in which the peer-to-peer and bottom-up dynamics of stakeholders in the short term meet the top-down dynamics of more advanced public agencies and government in the long term.

The Toolkit is designed as a website hosted in the Reflow web domain (www.reflowproject.eu) and featured as a sub-page within the Reflow website (<https://governance.reflowproject.eu/>). More information can be found in D4.3.

Figure 5: Illustration of the Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit

3.2.2 Internal feedback

The RCGT was primarily developed by WP4, although in close collaboration with other WPs and the pilot cities, and the production was based on a portfolio logic to trigger experimentation and learning across a full stack designed transition.

To coordinate the solution with the Reflow Framework, WP1 was highly involved in the initial design, and later in the process WP6 was involved to align with the work on capacity building.

The pilot cities have also been closely involved throughout the process. For instance, the content of the toolbox has been defined based on the tools used by the pilot cities during the Reflow Project, and their perceived usefulness. Further, the feature of “needs based” filtering of tools came out from interactions with pilot cities.

See D4.4 – Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit (RCGT) v1.1 for more information about the development of the toolkit.

3.2.3 External feedback, validation, and dissemination

The RCGT was further validated by external target audiences.

A survey was conducted in M32, led by IAAC, which aimed to assess insights for the implementation of the RCGT, and to propose a connection between the tools and practices documented in the toolkit and three main areas of intervention for flexible urbanism, i.e., ‘Open Connected Mixed’, ‘Iterative’, and ‘Commons-based and Polycentric cities. The respondents were invited to reflect, assess, and draw connections between the contextual barriers and possible solutions for overcoming them, by selecting multiple choice options and adding additional explanation about the decisions made. The solutions selected were finally connected to specific tools from the Reflow Collaborative Governance Toolkit. For instance, the respondents were asked about the case of the Berlin pilot and the challenge of open data in scaling the solution. Concretely, they were asked about the best approach for overcoming the barrier of “Individuals may lack knowledge, transparency and information about open data practices”. As seen in Figure 6, the majority identified “Collaborative definition of circular missions’ components and their interconnections” as the best approach. This approach connects to the RCGT tool “Circular Mission Wave”. Consequently, this tool was validated as a relevant tool for collaborative governance and intervention for flexible urbanism. The survey and its impact on the tool can be read in D4.4 – Collaborative Governance Toolkit v.1.1.

In addition to giving feedback on the relevance of the different tools, the respondents were also invited to give qualitative input and feedback on each pilot case, contributing to the section of ‘Toolkit in Practice’ on the RCGT website, where the governance structures of the pilot cities are described.

Figure 6. Example of question and answer from the survey on Collaborative Governance & Flexible Urbanism

Through this survey and the feedback on the usefulness of the tools, the RCGT website and the list of tools was restructured, and the filtering system based on needs was fine-tune and finalised.

The overview of target audiences which participated in the survey can be seen in Figure 7.

What is you main role? (Please, select one option)

6 responses

Figure 7: Respondents of survey on REFLOW Collaborative Governance and Flexible Urbanism

The RCGT has also received feedback from the Reflow Project's sister project Pop-Machina and iPRODUCE, and the Fab City Network. More specifically, the feedback was given on the connection of RCGT tools with Policy Briefs for Flexible Urbanism (Deliverable 4.5), and the identification of potential solutions that could be applied to support cities in overcoming specific challenges related to governance and flexible urbanism. Because of this external interaction, the application and effectiveness of RCGT tools could be improved based on real case scenarios.

After the feedback gathering, the Fab City Network states its interest in understanding how the RCGT and other Reflow governance resources could support the Fab City Network globally, showing external validation of the toolkit outside of the Reflow project.

3.3 Reflow Academy

3.3.1 Description

The Reflow Academy is a set of e-courses, case studies, webinars, and podcasts directly produced by the Reflow project to dig deeper into the main building blocks of the Reflow Framework.

E-courses: Three e-courses were developed based on the Reflow Framework: 1) Introduction to Circular Economy, 2) Governing Circular Economy in Cities, and 3) Circular Business Model Innovation for Regenerative Cities.

Case studies: During the Reflow Project, a collection of six case studies have been developed based on the learnings and outputs of the pilot cities in the Reflow project, based on each of the Reflow pilot cities. The purpose of these case studies is to link circular economy practice to the application of theory across a diversity of disciplines in higher educational settings. The case studies are presented in D6.5 – Collaborative Case Studies for Higher Education Curricula, where more details on the process including feedback and validation, can be found.

Webinars: Three webinars were held during the Reflow Project, exploring the topics of different WPs: WP3 Circular Engineering, WP4 Governance and Urban Strategies on Circular Economy, and WP2 IT Infrastructure and Tools. The webinars presented the work of the WP illustrated by the case of a specific pilot city and broadened the discussion by engaging an external expert.

Podcasts: The Reflow Academy has created and presented six podcasts about respectively Reflow in general, the Denim Deal, Circular Cities, Circular Business Models, Doughnut Cities, and Circular Jobs. All apart from the first, were based on a discussion with an external experts specific to the topic.

Figure 8: Illustration of the Reflow Academy

3.3.2 Internal feedback

E-courses: Invitations for beta-testing were sent to internal (REFLOW) individuals from different partner organisations to take the course of their choice and provide feedback through a dedicated Evaluation form. 15 individual reviewers took part in the beta-testing phase. Based on the feedback received during the beta-testing phase, a final iteration of the three courses was completed. Results of the beta-testing and evaluation is addressed in annex 1 of D6.4 Multi-Platform Digital Resources and Structured Learning Courses.

Case studies: With the pilot cities as the starting point for each case study, sifting through the topics, learnings, and inputs of the Work Packages in Reflow was used to pinpoint the content of the actual case. The development of case study dilemmas was co-created in collaboration with each of the pilot cities and were based on the real-life situations they found themselves in during the Reflow project. Data for the case studies were collected mainly through desk research and already existing data from other deliverables, as well as discussions with the pilot city representatives.

3.3.3 External feedback, validation, and dissemination

E-learning courses: The three e-learning courses were sent to different representatives of the target group (students, professors/teachers/experts in CE) for testing and content review of the courses prior to the official launch. This resulted in valuable, but minor adaptations, both in regards to content and technical aspects.

Case studies: The dilemma and structure of the cases was co-created with the Nordic case house. The Nordic Case House is part of the Teaching and Learning department at the Copenhagen Business School and seeks to promote the development of cases, their publishing and teaching. The CBS team approached the NCH team for gathering external expert feedback on the case studies as well as for tapping into important networks for testing,

feedback, and publishing. Internal Reflow partners, external faculty members across European higher educational institutions, and The Nordic Case House also provided feedback on each case study.

Webinars: The webinars included prominent external speakers, respectively Simon Clement, Senior Coordinator on Sustainable Economy and Procurement at ICLEI Europe and coordinator of City Loops, a sister project of Reflow, Claudia Alessio, Research Analyst at the Amsterdam-based foundation Circle Economy, and Stefan Sipka from the European Policy Centre (EPC). Their participation contributed greatly to the quality of the webinars and are examples of clustering with other organisations in the field of circularity in cities. Further, their acceptance to participate bears sign of the general interest of the topic and to the perceived professionalism of the Reflow Project, thus validating them as a relevant and interesting resource. Validation in the form of how many watched the webinar can be found in D7.3 Communication and Dissemination Activities Report.

Podcasts: As with the webinar, the inclusion of external experts signifies the clustering with other organisations and projects and signals the external validation of the importance and contribution of the Reflow Academy.

3.4 City ecosystem design and mapping methodology

3.4.1 Description

The City ecosystem design and mapping methodology is the process through which the pilot cities have developed a system change blueprint for their respective materials. The process was developed during the Reflow Project by Metabolic Institute and WAAG, and continuously re-iterated and updated. The process consists of an ecosystem mapping, goal setting, back-casting timelines, and stakeholder mapping. Although the individual components, such as the circular loops diagram, the back casting exercise and the stakeholder mapping are all well-established methods on their own, the innovation is in the full process and co-creation of the resulting action plan with the pilot cities.

Figure 9. Example of 1 step in the City Ecosystem design and mapping methodology

3.4.2 Internal feedback

This task builds its ground on a lot of existing knowledge coming from the work developed by pilots and WPs in the first years of Reflow project, and external resources and methods.

For instance, the circular loops diagram component of the methodology was developed using the Ellen McArthur butterfly diagram as a base, and back-casting timelines, and stakeholder mapping are well-known tools. The refining and translation of these existing tools and methods were done mainly by Metabolic, although in collaboration with WAAG, and with input from other WPs. During the project, the pilots have contributed actively to the development of the tasks through consistent input and discussion with the WPs, and also given direct feedback through the survey conducted by WP1 on the Reflow Platform, which can be read about in D1.4 - Validation and PFM Evaluation. In general, the tool was very well received by the pilot cities, who found all components useful, and particularly the MFA as a baseline for decision making.

3.4.3 External feedback, validation, and dissemination

The City Ecosystem Design and Mapping methodology was mainly developed during the last year of the project, as mentioned in close collaboration with other WPs and pilot cities. Within the project time frame the tool has not been subject to external feedback, however Metabolic is appreciating strong interest in the tool. Through their participation with a diverse and large range of projects across European cities on the topic of circularity, they have experienced a need for such an exercise when planning extensive and holistic system change. This points to a need for the asset also outside of the Reflow Project, and thereby indicates external validation of the usefulness of the tool.

4 Feedback, Validation, and Dissemination of the Pilots with target audiences

4.2 Introduction

In the following, the external interactions of each pilot is listed. This includes both feedback and validation on the solutions. Together, the two contribute indirectly to the dissemination of the solutions, and thereby complements the more dedicated dissemination activities (reported in D7.3 Communication and Dissemination Activities Report).

Feedback is understood as concrete comments, constrictive criticism, and advise which has contributed to the improvement of the solution.

Validation is understood as external endorsement of the solution as it is. This could be in the form of an invitation to present the solution, which signalises its relevance and novelty and thereby a sort of validation. It could also be expressed interest, intent or commitments from potential partners or customers.

To gather this information, each pilot was asked to provide an overview of its interactions with external actors, and listing the type of stakeholder, the type of interaction and the effect of the interaction, for each solution.

4.3 Amsterdam

The Reflow Amsterdam Pilot focuses on textiles. The pilot is targeting the way home textiles are discarded and reused, and how they can be returned to the local textile system. Currently, the challenge is that home textiles are often wrongly discarded due to a lack of awareness, and to sub-optimal ways of collecting textiles. More than 70% of home textiles in the pilot will eventually be incinerated rather than reused. Simultaneously, the demand for recycled material is growing slowly, due to an absence of commercial uptake. The Amsterdam Pilot has outlined three interconnected scenarios that tackle these challenges:

- Citizen scenario, short-term: Increase of home textiles collection at city-level by engaging citizens through an awareness campaign. The campaign is centred on changing the way citizens process their home textiles with the outcomes of discarding fewer textiles, and the extension of the textile lifecycle.
- Industrial scenario, long-term: Exchange Network to connect manufacturers to the collected consumer textiles to decrease the percentage of virgin textile fibres used. Several strategies assist new ways of collecting textiles to generate more feedstock for recycling industries and therefore support the production of new products with recycled resources.
- Policy scenario, long term: Focus on policy support through promoting a distributed governance system with bottom-up and top-down dynamics among governance, businesses, and citizens.

Through the three scenarios, the key target audience of Amsterdam's actions are citizens, who play a role in saving textiles from being discarded and contribute to textile life extensions. Additionally, the textile and recycling industry as well as designer and makers are of interest. In the following, the external interactions of Amsterdam and its stakeholder and target audience are laid out. The various interactions fostered the whole system approach of connecting citizen, industry, and policy. This has had an important impact on the development of the solutions, from ideation to fine-tuned results.

Feedback

Building a dialogue between the city council, civil society and private sector is crucial to identify the main regulatory and legal barriers as well as the sectors where actions can be taken. Therefore, external feedback on the developed solutions is central for further development and exploitation. In the following the feedback received on the pilots' actions and solutions by external stakeholders are presented. The description of the solutions can be found in D1.5 Project Impact Assessment.

The Swapshop: During an open call to action, with the aim of finding solutions for further use of discarded textiles, the Swapshop was chosen as the winner of the program, signifying some external feedback and validation from the very beginning.

The prototype was tested with a group of about 25 customers selected by the Swapshop.

Circular isolation gowns: The Amsterdam pilot worked with a group of stakeholders in the Amsterdam healthcare sector while developing alternative reusable products from a technological textile perspective. Amsterdam pilot produced a one-pager to initiate research using a grafted polymer on textiles jointly with the Italian CNR. Further, the pilot organized an event where different players in the textile industry could be activated and aligned into circular textile discussions. The Amsterdam pilot invited different

stakeholders and players within the textile industry to Pakhuis de Zwijgerin Amsterdam to discuss issues confronting the textile industry at the event, Monday Laundry Day. Together with the Municipality of Amsterdam and the Amsterdam Economic Board, roundtable talks were organized during this event to incite discussions and feedback on the solution.

United Repair Center: Similar as for the Circular Isolation Gowns, Amsterdam invited different stakeholders and actors to the Pakhuis de Zwijgerin Amsterdam to discuss issues confronting the textile industry at the event, Monday Laundry Day. Together with Amsterdam Economic board, Makersunite, Patagonia and other 70 stakeholders in the textile industry, roundtable talks were organized during the event to incite discussions and feedback on the solution. Multiple stakeholders were involved who wanted to participate in the pilot and Patagonia and social enterprise Makers Unite joined forces to run the first pilot of the United Repair Centre

The Amsterdam Reflow Booklet: In various meetings with BMA Techne and Waag, the municipality of Amsterdam discussed circular textile actions and approaches. During these meetings the need for shared knowledge on circular textile became noticeable to shape a common ground and understanding. To develop a holistic booklet, knowledge and experience needed to be disseminated from industry towards governance and policy makers.

City Wardrobe – indoor collecting: During community meetings with the municipalities of the MRA, textile collectors and textile sorting companies, the pilot aimed to session to understand what was lacking and why the current textile collecting system led to too much textile waste to be incinerated. The brainstorming sessions tackled the problem that collected textiles are often too contaminated or wet when collected traditionally. The meetings gave insights on the need for indoor collecting of textiles and to understand the different ways of collecting textiles such as on demand, indoor collecting, 24/7 textile street containers.

On-Demand Collection – Regman: In collaboration with Textielrace, Seenons, the municipality and Sympany the first pilot version of the solution was evaluated to measure the level of effectiveness and to understand if there is a need for an on-demand collection service. The pilot and evaluation made clear that citizens only make use of a on demand service when more waste streams are being collected rather than just one waste stream like textile.

Figure 10: Photo of the Reflow Amsterdam team visiting the textile collection point of Sympany

Markthal Innovation Lab: In various meetings with Boei (Markthal operator/developer), studio the Future, the municipality of Amsterdam and the mayor of Amsterdam, the general course of the Markthal Innovation Lab was discussed. It was first initiated as a place for community and food. Nevertheless, after these meetings it was decided that the Markthal should have a more creative, circular, and cultural (ccc) orientation.

Awareness Campaign: During a meeting with the Ellen MacArthur foundation and various fashion brands, the pilot shared its knowledge and received input about a similar campaign in New York.

Stadpas Card: An internal meeting between the municipal department on poverty reduction and waste and material aimed to find solutions on how citizens with lower income can participate in a circular economy. The outcome of the meeting, the Stadspas card is a service from the two departments on repairing cloth.

The Denim Deal: During the development of the solution, the collaborative governance approach has also been tested as an inclusive tool for identifying barriers and prioritizing opportunities through a central steering committee group. Local experiences by the pilot demonstrated that the ability to collaborate involves the delegation of certain tasks from formal government agencies to accredited companies, business associations or community organizations. Realistic best practices have been framed through a collective approach to support the identification and showcase solutions for increased plastic reuse, recovery, and reduction. In open discussion rounds of Dutch denim brands, House of denim, Ministry of infrastructure and water management, municipality, it was decided that the Denim deal remains open for until the end of the deal (2023), this differs compared to other green deals that are closed once signed. The main reason for this is the need to change an industry standard to use 20 % post-consumer cotton

textiles. National and international brands and suppliers are still able to sign the deal, which causes an increased impact of the initiative.

Across the local and national initiatives, the Amsterdam pilot has been invited to talk with actors globally, e.g., Pakistan, to discuss and align circular visions.

Validation

The awareness campaign and all included actions and events were validated through citizen's reactions. Focusing on citizen engagement, the overall stakeholder satisfaction with new models was analysed based on the Reflow Live Events at Pakhuis de Zwijger. An example of a live event was:

- Overall stakeholder satisfaction with new models: 93.5%
- I feel satisfied that many groups were represented at the live events such as governance, industry, research and education, and citizens: 84%

Further validation of the developed solutions are publications on the Knowledge Hub and reposts by stakeholders on social media such as LinkedIn. The commitment of stakeholders to the developed solutions can also be understood as validation. Due to the proven effectiveness of the Swapshop in avoiding carbon dioxide, the solution received further funding. This led to the opening of the Swapshop in Amsterdam and its connection to the Denim deal as provider of feedstock of non-reusable cotton items. Solutions such as Denim Deal, that uses tools from the RRG, lead to change in the urban context. Major industry brands are convinced and committed to the goals set by the Denim Deal to make denim circular and sustainable. For example, Scotch & Soda, MUD Jeans and Kuyichi will make three million jeans garments containing at least 20 per cent recycled textiles.

4.4 Berlin

The Reflow Berlin Pilot focuses on wastewater heat recovery to guide the city towards climate neutral heating. Wastewater heat is generated as a by-product of water use in industrial processes, and in the everyday domestic life of citizens. Wastewater produced by such processes often retains large amounts of thermal energy, but much of this heat potential is lost to the sewer system. To better utilize this resource, the Berlin Pilot seeks to map the potential of wastewater and related waste heat for its efficient recovery. This can further be matched with the demand for heat in the city. Greater awareness of this under-utilized energy source is an important component of a successful wastewater heat circular strategy. From a strategic point of view, the Berlin Pilot has been working on the development of a marketable solution, and on the development of wastewater heat. These are being considered as part of a robust, sustainable business model which will drive implementation across Berlin and other municipalities. The Berlin Pilot has outlined interconnected scenarios that tackle these challenges:

- Technology development
- Raising awareness and generating interest
- Implementation
- Exploitation or replication

Through these scenarios, the key target audience of Berlin's actions are different actors and organizations, which require different types of approaches. In particular, the Berlin pilots targets public and private property developers and city planners. Furthermore, the municipal decisions makers, i.e., the local senate agencies, are also identified as a key stakeholder group. In the following, the external interactions of Berlin, its stakeholder and target audience are laid out. The various interactions fostered the whole system approach of connecting citizen,

industry, and policy. This has had an important impact on the development of the solutions, from ideation to fine-tuned results.

Feedback

In the following section feedback on the Berlin solution from outreaches, events, conferences, meetings, and workshops are addressed. The Berlin Pilot has been invited to several conferences and to present in various forums, attaining significant feedback, several opportunities for partnerships, and potential collaboration with different stakeholders in the energy sector in Germany, and across Europe.

Outreach

As part of Berlin's approach of raising awareness and garnering interest in their solutions, the pilot reached out to industrial symbiosis partners to gather feedback regarding their solution. Operating as industrial symbiosis, by-products of one organisation become the raw materials for another⁷. This is particularly interesting for the further development of Berlin's solutions and the embedment in broader organisational systems, where wastewater heat potential can become raw material for industrial partners.

- Tyreman Group (Russia): *"The solution is great way for matchmaking which is the hardest part in our experience. I also think that your assumption regarding the potential for industrial symbiosis is correct. Recently we had a meeting with a start-up company willing to organize a vertical city farm for growing salads. They were looking for a place with cheap heat and clean water. I am sure it would be of great value for them to have this data when considering where to allocate their production. This is just an example; I am sure there is more to it"*.
- Thamsklyngen (Norway): *"The project sounds really interesting, and as you mention, it could be very useful for the industry. In this area we have a supplier that delivers heat from wastewater (from Elkem Thamshavn) both to private households and to the industry"*.
- Digipolis (Finland): *"The solution sounds interesting and useful in the context of industrial symbiosis. Potential of wastewater heat is even higher in industrial sites than in city buildings, but still large buildings and blocks can form useful source of wastewater heat. In my opinion, the software should also predict ways to utilize the waste heat, i.e., energy efficiency measures, external operations possibilities (heat transfer to food production, and so on). Factors for this in industry are normally; energy per day/month/year, power, substance, state of substance and temperature range. These factors provide needed information to make assumptions for ways to utilize to wastewater heat. One issue is to collect the data. So my question is how the software/application deals/collects the data per site/building/block? I think biggest question is relevant data collection, because coding/algorithm can be done inside the project team or by outsourcing"*.
- Kalundborg (Denmark): *"The app-solution sounds interesting as a way to steer supply and demand, which is something we absolutely can see a potential in contributing to/make use of"*.

Presentations:

At the conference hosted by DWA EnergieTag, the German Association for Water, Wastewater and Waste, the Berlin Pilot presented their methodology for the GIS- and simulation-based analysis of wastewater heat

⁷ European Commission. (2018). *Industrial Symbiosis*. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/environment/europeangreencapital/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/Industrial_Symbiosis.pdf

potentials. They were able to transfer new knowledge to other water utilities and receive feedback for further development and improvement. Similarly, at the annual German Heat Pump Forum in 2021, the Berlin pilot held a presentation for potential implementation, government, and dissemination partners. Significant interest was shown from the multiple stakeholders with many suggesting follow-up projects.

Figure 11: Photo of Daniel Heltzel, Director at Prototypes for Europe, presenting in Copenhagen

Workshops:

Through CityLab Berlin, the Berlin Pilot had a workshop together with construction companies in the Berlin-Neukölln, where they were able to brainstorm potential civic stakeholders in Berlin. CityLab Berlin as a nexus for discussion on new eas for city development between governments, civil society, academia, and start-ups shaped suitable platform for inspiration. The Berlin pilot left the workshop with both great encouragement and critical clues about the pilot app's potential to be used by stakeholders from the civil society, with the conclusion that the data should be as open as possible and with its relevance for civic stakeholders clearly addressed.

The Berlin pilot also had a defining workshop with expert Riccardo Klinger, the technical lead GIS at Toll Collect GmbH, a technology service provider for toll collection and enforcement in Germany. The workshop concerned Geo-Data infrastructures, combination of tools to implement Web-Map features and future possibilities to build upon this map with additional datasets from different industry branches. The workshop provided a perspective on how to expand the use of the wastewater radar in coupling with external data. Klinger showed strong interest for the solution.

In the Berlin pilot's workshop with their industry partner eZeit engineering office, they discussed a possible collaboration concerning the collection and simulation of heat demands of public and private buildings in Berlin. The successful workshop provided multiple possibilities of future partnerships concerning collecting, measuring, and simulating heat demand data. To further improve the efficiency of the Reflow map, simulations on district heat networks were also discussed. The workshop concluded with a clear categorization of different building types based on their primary heat usage which is now being used In the Map.

Towards the end of the Reflow project, May 2022, the Berlin pilot held a workshop with infrastructure companies of Berlin, organised in the "infralab". This session aimed to check if properties of the partners are suitable for wastewater heat utilisation and to elaborate opportunities of shared heat supply and was done through a data driven approach using the GIS-based potential data set of BWB and the partner's property data. Partners include major energy suppliers and the public transportation company (Vattenfall, GASAG, BVG, BSR, BWB and Stromnetz Berlin).

Meetings:

In Copenhagen, the Berlin Pilot presented their entire solution to the public/private institution HOFOR, the capital regions utilities company. The aim was to retrieve feedback and explore the radars potential use in Copenhagen/Denmark. However, HOFOR is operating with district heating, and therefore wastewater heat is not fitting in Copenhagen. They would also not allocate space for wastewater heat capture pumps in the sewer system, as they would rather keep the space for water in the event of heavy rainfall.

The pilot also met with Vattenfalls district heating department, one of the largest producers and distributors of district heating in Europe to discuss a co-operation on combining the district heating grid and wastewater heat potentials in preparation for a future feasibility study. The meeting provided perspectives on how to expand the use of wastewater radar in coupling with external data. The meeting showed strong interest, and the first collaboration between Berlin Water Management Agency and Vattenfall will be for a single location.

Validation

Various workshops and the participation at events of the circular community of Germany, show the general interest in Berlins' solutions. Further, the wastewater heat map was published at the Knowledge Hub and local as well as international stakeholder published and reposted content about the Pilot's actions on social media such as LinkedIn. Berlin's solutions are developed on the premises to contribute to the UN Sustainability Development Goals, which as such validate the actions of the Berlin pilot.

Firstly, the City of Berlin is committed to implementing circular economic practices and material flows. Based on 1) BWB being a Reflow consortium partner and 2) CityLAB being a cooperation partner to the Berlin Pilot, the Berlin pilot team assumes that Berlin is interested in becoming an innovation leader if it comes to wastewater heat recovery.

Further, feedback of third parties on the Berlin pilot was very positive throughout. Wastewater heat recovery was met with curiosity and interest whenever team members brought up the topic. The project idea was presented in informal, yet structured reach-outs to an Honorary Member of the Club of Rome, to a senior member of the European Investment Bank, to the City of Mannheim, to the former Managing Director of the Rockefeller Foundation and to an author of the 'Climate Finance Decision Making Tree' (ICLEI). In all cases, it was agreed to share more information. The Berlin pilot assumes the interest is particularly high because few people think about wastewater heat recovery when considering approaches to climate change.

Through their out-reach they were also in contact with other projects and industry institutions such as the HOOP EU project and the Finnish Industry, to validate and scope the potential for scaling the solution beyond Berlin.

At an event organized by HOOP, the Reflow wastewater heat pilot presented the solution for the HOOP consortium members and invited guests. HOOP is an EU project that supports eight lighthouse cities and regions develop large-scale urban circular bioeconomy initiatives with focus is on recovering resources from urban biowaste and wastewater to make bio-based product. Their focus is on recovering resources from urban biowaste and wastewater to make bio-based products. The participation at the event resulted in information on exploitation

possibilities in other cities. There was a very high interest for the Berlin solution, and it was agreed to further networking activity.

In Finland, the Berlin Pilot had two meetings with Finnish industry and research experts on wastewater heat – brainstorming about the feasibility of technology and exploitation to other cities, particularly Helsinki, Tampere, and Turku in Finland. The input from these meetings were very positive and gave valuable insights into reaching out to other cities. The meetings concluded with an agreement of further talks.

The Berlin Pilot also had meetings with the architecture office Schmidt Hammer Lassen from Copenhagen in Denmark discussing the relevance of the technology for real estate developers and architecture firms. The meeting revealed high relevance for architecture firms, particularly for district heating and large building complexes. There was agreed to have more talks in the future.

The Berlin pilot was in contact with Local Governments for Sustainability (ICLEI), a global network of more than 2500 local and regional governments committed to sustainable urban development, to discuss utilizing their tool on financing instruments in the energy sector. In the meeting the parts agreed on a cooperation should the tool be needed.

Lastly, BWB held an expert workshop on wastewater heat recovery technology in May 2022. Participants included four major infrastructure firms of Berlin: (i) Berliner Stadtreinigungsbetriebe (BSR), which handles waste management in Berlin, (ii) Berliner Verkehrsbetriebe (BVG), the city's public transportation company, (iii) Stromnetz Berlin, the operator of the city's electricity grid and (iv) Vattenfall, a large energy provider.

Michel Gunkel and Heinrich Guertler, working in the R&D Department at BWB, presented the current status of wastewater heat utilization in Berlin as well as the recently conducted potential analysis. Daniel Heltzel, Director at technology transfer firm Prototypes for Europe (www.prototypes.berlin), introduced the audience to the REFLOW project and the Wastewater Heat Radar that had been developed as part of REFLOW in Berlin.

Participants had the opportunity to see the radar in action by using addresses of buildings they own. All four organizations maintain a significant number of buildings in the city for their own operations. The technology was very well received by the participants. It was agreed to explore the opportunities arising out of the work performed in the REFLOW project in the very next future.

Figure 12. Picture from presentation for infrastructure firms in Berlin. Source: Berlin Pilot

4.5 Cluj-Napoca

The goal of the Reflow Cluj-Napoca pilot is the improvement of the energy efficiency of public and residential buildings across the city. The pilot aimed, within the Reflow project, to assess the impact of the current measures taken to date by the city on the energy efficiency of selected buildings and to involve local stakeholders in implementing these measures. In parallel, the pilot hopes to stimulate different actors within the ecosystem to propose new innovative ideas regarding the integration of renewable energy sources while educating them on the city's circular economy strategy. The Cluj-Napoca pilot has outlined three interconnected scenarios that tackle these challenges:

- Awareness rising and ecosystem support: this scenario focuses on implementing the energy transition through increased citizen and stakeholder awareness.
- Physical infrastructure and technology innovation: this scenario seeks to realise the energy transition in the city through retrofitting infrastructure and collection and analysis of energy data.
- Policy infrastructure: this scenario aims to influence policy makers towards integrating circular actions energy efficient principles into local policies.

Through these three scenarios, the key target audience of Cluj-Napoca's actions are public authorities, schools, universities, research institutions and other public institutions administered by the municipality. Further, businesses and industrial clusters, especially T&C and energy but also furniture, agriculture and creative industries are of interest. In the following, the external interactions of Cluj-Napoca and its stakeholder and target audience are laid out. The various interactions fostered the whole system approach of connecting citizen, physical infrastructure and policy. This has had an important impact on the development of the solutions, from ideation to fine-tuned results.

Feedback

Working towards the release of these outputs, the pilot has carried out meetings with the stakeholders to map the needs, capabilities and opportunities for action related to energy efficiency and circular economy at the municipal level. To finalize and scale the solutions of the pilot, it is crucial to engage with specific target groups based on their certain ecosystems. In the following, the feedback received on the pilot's actions and solutions, by external stakeholders are presented.

The Retrofit kit: The pilot has carried out a collaborative process between local partners and the ecosystem in the design of the solution. The pilot hosted a series of stakeholder mapping meetings where the pilot team identified an important number of actors that were willing to contribute to the development of an innovative, yet affordable solution to increase energy efficiency. Cluj-Napoca then invited these actors to a series of meetings (in a brainstorm-like format) to identify the best pathway for action. The meetings concluded that the pilot would install a hardware –software package (consisting of smart sockets, LED lighting system, light and movement sensors, new electric panels and connections and a smart metering system + monitoring software) in the dormitory of the "Energetic" Highschool in Cluj-Napoca. This solution is cross-cutting through Cluj-Napoca's pilot city action, in the sense that, it will also serve as both a case study and project for current electrical technician students. In collaboration with the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca (lead stakeholder) and other energy efficiency stakeholders, the solution was constantly adjusted according to feedback and outcomes of the meetings carried out through the process.

Energy Map: During meeting with TREC members, ideas and approaches on the creation of a renewable energy map were collected and integrated. The outcome of these meeting states the sort of data that has been and needs to be collected to compose a systemized energy map. The outcome of the meetings and the energy map function as input for future policy and investment proposals.

Research and development: During several conferences, the pilot presented its development and circular solutions to researchers and the community. The pilot received feedback and adjustment suggestion to its solutions such as suggestions for themes and examples introduced in the master's course.

Figure 13. Photo from meeting with stakeholders

Validation

The work of the Cluj-Napoca pilot has received approval both nationally and internationally.

- Various workshops and the participation at Transylvanian Cluster International conference 2021, show the general interest in Cluj-Napoca solutions.
- The Retrofit kit solution was published at the Knowledge Hub and local as well as international stakeholder published and reposted content about the pilots' actions on social media such as LinkedIn.
- The pilot pitched a course on Circular Economy, which was integrated to the master's program of sustainable development at the School of Economics (Babeş-Bolyai University of Cluj-Napoca).
- The integrated Urban Development Strategy will be followed in the years to come, with an increased focus on circularity, resulting in a Circular City Action Plan on the medium term.

4.6 Milan

The Reflow Milan Pilot focuses on supporting the transition to a circular food system. It does this by connecting fundamental actors involved in the tracking and distribution of food throughout the city. The Milan Pilot initiated a series of activities around co-creation, co-design, and co-production to facilitate a systematic transition of the Milanese urban food system to a circular model for agri-food products, such as fruit, vegetables, cereals, meat, fish,

and dairy. To make this systemic change possible, the Milan pilot needed to develop a new way of operating within the value chain based on the tracking of materials and processes to the key players of the urban food system. To set the stage for this change, the Milan pilot's development pathway was founded on connecting a multitude of different actors in the urban food system, including large municipal enterprises, wholesalers, universities, FabLabs, and makerspaces, and allowing for possible paths of circular and social innovations to emerge from these collaborations. This was approached in different scenarios:

- Local economy goal: to optimize circular practices among different multi-scale stakeholders of the Milan food value chain
- Policy goal: to enhance the municipal covered markets and the general food market of Milan respectively as community hubs for the neighbourhoods and place to avoid food waste
- Awareness goal: involve NGOs, active consumers, citizens on circular economy campaigns on fight against food waste
- Public-Private Partnership goal: involve local businesses to participate in public and private partnership processes to enhance public spaces as drivers for local economy in peripheral areas of Milan.

Through these scenarios, the key target audience of Milan's actions are public authorities, vendors, SMEs, and municipal covered markets. Further, business, and industrial clusters, especially agriculture and the food industries are from interest. In the following, the external interactions of Milan and its stakeholder and target audience are laid out. The various interactions fostered the whole system approach of connecting citizen, physical infrastructure, and policy. This has had an important impact on the development of the solutions, from ideation to fine-tuned results.

Feedback

To provide solutions for the Milan food industry that would create value for food actors, reduce food waste and create a positive impact in the city, the Milan pilot has been deeply involved with its stakeholders to understand their challenges, pain points, needs and incentives to reduce food waste. From the start of the project to its end the Milan pilot has thus been tightly involved with relevant stakeholders for each phase of the project, receiving defining feedback that has been forwarded into the following phases. The following sections gives a rough outline of the feedback received at various stages in the process, starting with the general input on the scenarios of Milan, before describing some key external feedbacks for the solutions.

Political consensus building (Municipality of Milan): Together with the municipality of Milan and its various departments (Urban Economy and Employment; Commerce, Food Policy Office), the Milan Pilot organised a brainstorming on the Reflow goals and its possible synergies with other policy areas. The input gave valuable insights into the idea to include Reflow among "circular food" actions and to work on food markets (both at neighbourhood level and urban level) as relevant nodes for agri-food material flows at the urban level.

Agreement between the Municipality of Milan and Sogemi: The Milan pilot held a presentation of the project and its objectives to the Sogemi top management. The input was decisive for the result of having Sogemi onboard. They decided to participate in the project with the Municipality of Milan, as Reflow is particularly in line with some of the Company's strategic objectives on the circular economy. And agreement was consequently drafted.

Hands-on research: analysis of selected covered markets: Hands-on research was conducted on 5 municipal covered markets which were selected by Milan municipality with support of AssoFood (representative of markets) and the market managers. Visits to the five markets and interviews with market vendors provided data showing a clear picture of market activities in terms of sustainable and circular practices. The analysis was very useful, and the Milan team could consequently proceed with the next project phases.

Stakeholder engagement and validation of pilot scenarios: The Milan Pilot had meetings and a co-creation workshop with external stakeholders, which included public companies such as Sogemi and Amsa; the NGO for food donation - Recup; Ibrida - a startup for beer production from unsold bread, as well as Il Giardinone and Krill Design, and NGO and an agency with projects about saving coffee grounds.

There were conducted one-to-one meetings to understand the stakeholders' potential interests and synergies with Reflow. The meetings with NGOs and start-ups defined the final panel of actors to be involved in the next co-design phase and to have them on board. The final co-creation workshop with Sogemi, Amsa and Milan Food Policy was held to co-create and identify Milan pilot scenarios. Through the workshop a final list of 5 pilot scenarios were developed. From the scenarios, Milan partners developed concept solutions, and a final list of three use-cases were validated to start the co-design phase managed by the three Fab Labs.

Food Market 4.0

The Food Market 4.0 solution was tested within the Morsenchio Municipal Covered Market, in collaboration with a market vendor, SoGeMi and the boxes provider (CPR system26).

The definition and validation of the Food Market 4.0 Dashboard scenario was co-designed in a workshop led by Polyfactory, a research laboratory and fab lab of the Politecnico di Milano. Stakeholders included Comune di Milano, WeMake, OpenDot, SO.GE.MI - FOODY, Amsa/A2A, Morsenchio Municipal Covered Market, RECUP, SoDe (Social Delivery), E-Novia (Measy) and Unes. The workshop generated concepts and possible solutions around the topic of Markets as neighbourhood logistics hubs which provided valuable inputs for the definition and validation of the Market 4.0 Dashboard scenario

Foody Zero Waste

Four design workshops with stakeholders and one meeting involving RECUP and the Italian Red Cross provided continuous feedback and validations to the Milan Pilot on the development of the solution.

The first co-design workshop was held together with RECUP and the Italian Red Cross. This session involved a review of the material flow between RECUP and the Italian Red Cross, as well as to validate the proposed solution. This enabled the stakeholders to see the prototype and agree on the proposed solution. It also provided constructive feedback on how to better implement the designed solution

The second co-design workshop was held with RECUP and designed to check every step of the designed solution. The session helped to better define all the features RECUP needed within the solution to validate the steps of the whole process.

The third co-design workshop with stakeholders such as SO.GE.M.I., RECUP, OpenDot and WeMake was held to review the flow analysis and to highlight the critical touchpoints for SO.GE.M.I and RECUP. The session provided constructive feedback for the development of the solution, and it helped to highlight the stakeholder's way of working as well as their practical need.

After the initial workshops a meeting was recalled to improve the Italian Red Cross' and Recups understanding of the prototype feature and to coordinate the practical side of the prototyping phase and to test the prototype. Both stakeholders were involved in a practical test of the developed solution, to make sure everything is clear ahead of the testing phase.

The fourth co-design workshop was held together with the SO.GE.M.I wholesalers Casagrande, Gala Fruit as well as Local Producers President. The session was helpful to get a better understanding of the wholesalers' way of working, and to define what was needed to support the donation of surplus food.

Lastly a meeting was held, at the SO.GE.M.I headquarter, to validate the solution, its process and the next steps with all the stakeholders involved in the project: RECUP, the Italian Red Cross, SO.GE.M.I., Food Policy, Wholesalers and Babaco and the Milan Municipality. The Foody Zero Waste scenarios and the solution was presented, providing a space where everyone could get a better understanding of the solution, its prototyping and testing phase. The session also contributed to having the various stakeholders discuss the interactions related to the donations and led to an agreement on the flow and processes.

The final feedback before the end of the project was the test period done by RECUP, where 8.7 tonnes of food was recovered over 4 interventions at the SO.GE.M.I foodmarket, using the BOTTO, showing the usefulness of the solution for all stakeholders.

Figure 14. Picture from testing of BOTTO at the Market of Milano Foody SO.GE.M.I and wholesalers

Prima Seconda:

A co-design and co-creation workshop hosted with participants from Ibrida Birra, Comune di Milano, WeMake and OpenDot. The aim of the session was to explore the use-case scenario, design a value flow and identify circular loops and solutions. The co-design workshop resulted in a concept of the use case scenario and requirements.

Validation

As the feedback section above demonstrated the Milan pilot has been working with a range of external stakeholder in relation to all their different solutions. Their solution has received wide recognition and interest from the involved stakeholders showing that that they have touched upon a very timely issue.

Foodmarket 4.0

The solution Foodmarket 4.0 solution was published at the Knowledge Hub and local as well as international stakeholder published and reposted content about the pilots' actions on social media such as LinkedIn.

In February of 2022, the Milan team was also invited to present the solution *BOTTO* at the first of four yearly roundtables, hosted by the Fab City Foundation, a foundation supporting projects and educational programs that are focused on building the capacity of cities and their communities. 80 people attended, mostly from scientific community and industry. The invitation reflects the general interest that has been shown for the Milan solution across Europe and is a great validation of the team's work.

Foody Zero Waste - external expert validation: Organised through the Reflow consortium, a meeting was setup between Saimon Skurichin, founder & CEO of BRØL, the World's 1st Circular Brewery, and Irene Di Lauro, a prominent food activist in Copenhagen. The aim of the meeting was to gain validation on the Milan solutions replicability in a different city. The meeting provided validation both on the urgency of the problem and on the replicability of the solution, despite the difference of environment.

- **Impressed:** The experts were impressed that the Milan Pilot had gotten the wholesalers to use the solution. In Copenhagen the consensus is that wholesalers want to do the least possible, which was also a problem that the Milan team could recognize. However, with several concrete arguments such as the price of waste management and the value of the data collection the Milan solution provided a convincing argument for both the wholesalers and the municipality.
- **The value of data:** For Foodsharing Copenhagen, collection of data would also be of high value, as wholesalers would know how much they have saved. In Foodsharing they have been operating with manually entering data into a dashboard with little structure. By law in Denmark, you must show the quantity and type of food collected. Henceforth the organisation expressed high enthusiasm for using a solution such as Botto, also from the foodsharing perspective, as it would save time on data collection.

- **Replicability to Copenhagen:** Overall the experts were positive to adapting such a solution in Copenhagen and conversely the Milan team could confirm that Botto can easily be updated which makes it replicable to different needs and different environments. Even the telegram bot can be customized to be adapted to other stakeholders. E.g., it could potentially also be extended to citizens, which would to a higher degree resonate with the model of Foodsharing Copenhagen. However, as a non-profit organization and intermediary, Foodsharing Copenhagen would not be able to pay for the device. Finding a payee would pose a challenge.

4.7 Paris

The Reflow Paris Pilot focuses on city-wide timber and wood use in the temporary construction industry, including events. The Pilot sets out to quantify and qualify the waste material flows generated from such temporary use, through the development of new models and digital tools. These tools are aimed at facilitating the reuse of wood materials and products to contribute to the acceleration of circular models in this sector. By identifying and quantifying these material flows, wood can be monitored and reintegrated into manufacturing processes, extending the material lifecycle. Besides this track-and-trace function, these tools can generate databases of wood products. The goal of this inventurisation is to support the development of an agile digital marketplace that will increase material exchange between the events industry and the temporary construction sector. The Paris pilot focused on three interconnected scenarios:

- **Equip:** this scenario aims to ensure that reusable wood material is available in an efficient way and that all interested actors have access to a pool of material and digital tools.
- **Design:** this scenario seeks a change in usage and design of wood material towards reusability between different events and actors.
- **Raise awareness and evaluate:** this scenario focuses on awareness raising about circular practices, reusable resources among professionals in the construction and event industry.

Through these three scenarios, the key target audience of Paris's actions are event actors and temporary structures, viewed as waste generators. On the opposite reuse actors, and innovative project developers, viewed as waste users are benefiting of the pilots' solutions. Logistical actors and coordinators are the link between waste generators and waste users to facilitate a circular wood flow, thus are also relevant stakeholders. The solutions can only be implemented through the collaboration with the city's ecosystem and the key stakeholders such as makers, designers, architects, urban farmers, and innovators, who offer their expertise and inspiration on the development of circular economy in Paris. In the following, the external interactions of Paris and its stakeholder and target audience are laid out. The various interactions fostered the whole system approach of connecting waste generators, waste users and the facilitators between these actors. This has had an important impact on the development of the solutions, from ideation to fine-tuned results.

Feedback

The development of the Paris pilot over the Reflow project's timespan has involved the collaboration of 23 stakeholders who have provided counselling activities over the course of this period to guide and direct the Paris pilot. These activities have provided valuable contributions to the Paris pilot which has helped to shape the development of their prototypes, refine their focus, gather important feedback and to test their solutions in the real-world. For example, understanding the real needs of resource centres and the challenges which actors of the

cultural sector are faced with towards their circular transition helped to pinpoint and orient the co-development of the Paris pilot's solutions Re-Label and Dimension-use to incorporate these conditions. An overview of the counselling activities with stakeholders is listed below, including their influence on the pilot's direction. In the following, the feedback received on the pilot's actions and solutions, by external stakeholders are presented.

Dimension-use: During the development of the Dimension-use, the pilot constantly collaborated with stakeholders, important for the Improvement and further development of the solution.

Together with the stakeholder Plaine Commune, the pilot co-developed a joint software, facilitating reuse in the construction sector. The team was elaborating a platform for reused materials on their territory in order to connect emitters to receivers. During this, the need to connect the different databases to have a broader and coherent catalogue on the territory of Plaine Commune, was outlined. Further feedback was given during the development of the Dimension-use software and use, in collaboration with IT-Link. WAO Architecture, as a project incubated by Driven, the data entry level development was brainstormed on. Further, Restore (an association of professionals working on circular economy in the construction/ event sector and Extramuros (a resource center), gave feedback on the prototyping process of the device. The stakeholders were brainstorming about their needs regarding the reconditioned materials they like to use for their projects. Focus was on the question: what are the difficulties they encounter while retrieving those materials and how to improve their experience. Through these sessions, the drop-down menus for the dimension-use interface were implemented (key words for the materials characterizations).

After the initial development state, La Ressourcerie du Cinéma (Karine d'Orlan de Polignac, Jean Roch Bonin), were testing the prototype. Through their feedback, the prototype was tested and the Dimension-use prototype was improved, related to their resource centre management. As the Ressourcerie du Cinéma is a new resource centre, insights on the resource managements were given to codevelop new processes to integrate the Dimension-use. Concrete outcomes of the testing were the redesign on the user experience for the software interface and the user experience design for the online platform.

Kanso & Co offered counselling on the implementation of Reflow OS to the solution. The aim was to develop the process to merge the dimension-use platform with the WELoop interface in the future.

Paris SAS: Safi-salon – maison et objet, offered counselling and feedback on the recuperation process of wood to set-up during large fairs. Throughout this process, in a learning by doing approach, the pilot started to develop understanding of the key actors involved and how to integrate within their activities. A finding was that the dimension-use has to be used on the storage site and cannot be used on the event site during dismantling, as the logistics are too fast. Trough counselling of Reed-Expo-FIAC, on the same topic, emphasized the need to clearly identify the state of the material before dismantling.

RE-Label: La Réserve des Arts and Ville de Paris had discussions about reuse of material in future laws. The discussion allowed understanding the importance of reuse not only in architecture and construction activities but also in design and micro architecture. The pilot then started implementing a strategic reflection around the label criteria and as a new legislative standard.

Further feedback was collected through surveys by Volumes, Woma, and Morning. During a series of meetings with fablabs and workshops the possible variables which could be implemented by the Label were discussed.

These discussions highlighted the needs in the workshops around the good practice guide and the definition of a community attached to the Label. Further, it gave insights on the development of the specific studies of the different workshops on interior design aspects, available tools, members, designers, users of the places. A survey with future beneficiaries of the relabel, designers, creatives from the Fab City Store community, on Re label, showed the needs of stakeholders. Through these exchanges, the pilot had a better understanding of the needs of solutions for easier access to reemployment (logistical assistance, setting up a network of mutual aid between actors, exchange of raw materials, etc.).

During brainstorming sessions with designers and engineers (François Brument, Sonia Laugier, Jonah Maars) further details of the label were given feedback on. Focus was on the Label's principles, criteria and variables, its implementation on designs to document the life of circular projects, both on objects and online. Further brainstorming was done on the reflection around a citizen and professional portal to allow better consumer accessibility to responsible products and facilitate the use of reusable materials to workshops and designers.

After this working session, the pilot confirmed the desire to focus on the narrative of materials and objects, on the relationships between the actors of reuse, design and workshops.

Presentations and workshops, under the premises of education and sensitization, engaged the National Art and Design School Nancy, Mines National Engineers School, ICN Business School. During an interactive workshop on Miro the stakeholders engaged in debates and discussions and to validate the need for a label and support with a guide of best practices for young designers and young professionals. Their questions and comments made the pilot rethink the project and redirect the project more adapted to young professionals. Further workshops with young professionals showcased the importance of training and transmitting the relabel methodology to be well adapted to designers, makers, architects. The interventions highlight a new practice of circular economy and wood reuse, confirming the use of the label. The feedback allowed the pilot to improve the contents of the workshop. During a step-by-step experimentation of the online platform of re-label with creatives from the Fab City Store community the pilot collected feedback on the platform and opened optimization for the platform according to the user's needs.

To enlarge and ensure the scope of the label, the pilot had on boarding meetings with (potential) partners for Re-Label. Utopies and OPEO confirmed next collaborations around the importance of the Re-label methodology applied to territories. The stakeholders are measuring the possibilities to join forces to improve local manufacturing and economy. Through RFFlabs and Réseau Français des Fablabs, the pilot received feedback on enlarging the scope of the label at a national level, understanding the needs of the community and the importance of the economic aspects of the label.

Driven Start-up Studio: The studio invited Vinci, ENPC, SPie Batignolles, Bollinger & Grohmann, Impulse Partners, La Forge, Atelier WOA, Poolp, as Participants to the incubation challenge session at the Driven Demo Day. Through the feedback, the solution was able to sharpen and highlight the importance of its MVP (minimum viable product) to validate start up idea in real-case scenarios. To validate the market interest at the studio's services, the pilot gathered feedback interest from academic and research institution to spin-off and fund projects and ideas generated in research groups through the studio platform. In brainstorming sessions with IAAC - Advanced Architecture Group, the impact on the construction industry and the services of the studio were further discussed.

During on-boarding sessions, the studio received feedback on the market interest and confirmed partnerships of stakeholders such as Bollinger+Grohmann or Noumena Group/ Reshape.

In collaboration with the city hall of Paris, the pilot participated at workshops with actors from the cultural sectors to identify key challenges with the transition towards circular economy. During these roundtable discussions, the pilot received validation of their activities as they are in line with the key challenges of optimising storage and get more visibility on material availability, in a circular re-use system. Further, the pilot discussed on how to facilitate the implication of cultural actors in the MFA process. Cultural actors we presented the MFA process and asked for feedbacks on how to integrate data collection activities to their current activities and on how to convince cultural actors of the needs to follow material flows. As an outcome, the pilot emphasized the data security and privacy aspects of the data to reassure actors when participating.

Validation

The Paris pilot has been in touch with the Office de tourisme Paris (OCTP) which is the tourism office of the City of Paris where they presented Reflow and the work being undertaken by the pilot city. OCTP was also invited to the Pecha Kucha Paris Night, an event hosted by the Paris pilot partner, Volumes. At the event, the issues of tourism in Paris were presented and with specific attention to the issues that the member of the OCTP (professionals) are facing within this sector and the actions which could be taken to create sustainable and circular events. Out of these proceeding, the Paris pilot succeeded in enhancing the conversation on sustainable development across tourism professionals. The Reflow project within Paris was important and useful in convincing them that practices in the field of tourism and large events held in the city need to change. Some of the changes already experienced within this field has included the end of single-use plastics. A link between the association La Réserve des Arts and the Reflow Paris pilot was established through the involvement of the Social Economy and Circular Economy Office at the launch of the project and across different meetings throughout the project period. The connection to La Réserve des Arts is a key fundament for the Reflow Paris pilot to further inspire and contribute to changes as the association is an operator which organizes reuse materials from cultural events and who aim to support cultural, creative, and the crafts sector in incorporating circular economy practices and the reuse of materials.

In addition to these acts of contribution and inspiration from the Reflow Paris pilot, other offices and departments in France have been involved with the team through presentations and meetings. These have included:

- The City of Paris, Green Spaces and the Environment Department
- Les Canaux, the operator who gathers social economy actors
- French Event Booster, an incubator linked with Paris&Co (the innovation agency)
- We Love Green, a big music festival in Paris involved in sustainable development

In relation to the context presented above, Reflow and the solutions the Paris pilot will produce are particularly important for the City of Paris and beyond. This is because the circular economy solutions and business models the Paris pilot will design and develop will be put to the test ahead of the Olympic Games in 2024.

The Paris pilot and its work with the circularity of wood and temporary construction was also shown high relevance when invited to present the work at one of the webinars organised by Veltha, an International Research Association established based in Belgium in 2010 which works on Research in the field of Sustainable Development and Circular Economy⁸. The webinar was done in collaboration with CityLoops, on the subject of Urban Transformation across Europe. The recording can be found online⁹.

An important validation was from Maison & Objet, the “go-to platform for the design sector”, which previously provided important feedback for the Paris pilot across solutions. For the March 2022 edition of their annual trade show, the Paris pilot made an exhibition dedicated to the circular economy. During the 2021 edition, the team collecting as much wood as they could, and transform it into a complete scenography system to be shown in 2022. To do this, they stored the wood at Re-Store, digitized it in a database through the Dimension-use, and designed a flexible and modular scenography that could host objects and printings, to show an alternative to disposable event architecture. The design was co-created with external designers. In total, more than 30 externals were involved, and the exhibition was well received. Several companies and actors offered the Paris pilot the opportunity to collaborate on similar projects.

⁸ Veltha. (2022). *About us*. Retrieved from Veltha: <https://www.veltha.eu/about-us/>

⁹ Veltha. (2022). *Loops 2.0 #7: a discussion with Reflow and City loops*. Retrieved from Veltha: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fxkcx74MlnY&t=21s&ab_channel=Veltha

Figure 15. Picture from the exhibition during Maison&Objet 2022 edition.

Lastly, the Dimension-use has obtained an 88 percent stakeholder satisfaction amongst beta-testers and potential future users. The satisfaction was calculated based on a survey which was sent to a limited number of people, as the product is not publicly available in the market yet, which is becoming quite competitive. Another useful KPI is "The extent to which the project has contributed to, or inspired, changes in municipal rules and regulations to support implementation and "mainstreaming". Details about these KPIs can be found in D1.5 Project Impact Assessment.

4.8 Vejle

The Reflow Vejle pilot focuses on plastic waste by gaining insights into urban plastic consumption and increasing the circularity of the city's plastic value chains. The accumulation of non-recyclable plastic, plastic-based waste, and its poor management is a problem faced by Vejle. Working closely with diverse test sites, covering retailers, manufacturers, healthcare facilities and an innovation center, the Vejle pilot has gained valuable insights into the bottlenecks of plastic use, and recycling behaviour in the city. The Vejle pilot places a significant emphasis on its citizens as change makers towards reaching the Vejle pilot's long-term goal of circular plastics. This citizen focus

is evident in the solutions that have been developed by the Vejle pilot, which seek to activate a citizen movement by empowering them to become informed and active in the change-making.

- The pilot's short-term objectives are: To generate better sorting at the test-sites and amongst the citizens in Vejle. This involves an increased knowledge of how to sort plastic waste and awareness about plastic alternatives. They also strive to unlock possibilities to improve reducing, reusing and recycling of plastics in a local context.
- The long-term objectives are: To change the plastic streams and create circular streams of specific plastic types. This involves activating a citizen movement with an empowered local community of active and informed citizens, and new solutions to foster methods and tools to reuse plastic and replace plastic in products.

Through these three scenarios, the key target audience of Vejle's actions are citizens, private households, and students. Further, businesses, entrepreneurs, and makers as well as policy makers are important stakeholders of Vejle's solutions. In the following, the external interactions of Vejle and its stakeholder and target audience are laid out. The various interactions fostered the whole system approach of connecting waste generators, waste users and the facilitators between these actors. This has had an important impact on the development of the solutions, from ideation to fine-tuned results.

Feedback

The contribution of experts in Vejle has guided both the initial direction of the work, and to fine-tune the solutions. Three yearly committee meetings were held with the Reflow Vejle steering group. The meetings provided a platform for continuous feedback on the project's development.

The local steering group committee, consists of the following participants:

- Aage Vestergaard Larsen, recycling factory (private company)
- Politicians, Nature and Environment Committee
- Fablab - Spinderihallerne (public/private institution)
- Innovation and Entrepreneurship + Waste and Environmental Dep., Vejle Municipality (public institution)
- The Danish Environmental Protection Agency (public institution)
- AAB, housing association (private institution)
- Local committee - West of Vejle (citizen)
- Sofiegården (elderly care center - public institution)

This group has a governing function and has been highly involved in the development of Reflow in Vejle. In particular, the process on selecting test sites and prototypes for Reflow in Vejle. To proceed with the test sites, rating them has been based on data from the plastic waste analysis, material flow analysis and feedback from the board. Rating on how to prioritize the prototypes has been based on its potential impact.

Actively involving the community for feedback has also been an important aspect during the implementation of the project. Three communities have been involved with:

- 1) The local steering group committee,
- 2) The political committee, NMU (Nature & Environment)
- 3) Working groups at the test sites (Sofiegården, REMA 1000, and Den Gamle Gård).

50 meetings and workshops has been held with the different communities, translating into important decisions to be made regarding the Vejle pilot, including choosing the test sites and gathering understandings of the everyday life of those who live at the test sites. Through these inputs, the Vejle pilot could shape their decisions and implementation around informed insights from the community. Looking for initiatives and networking between social actors and citizens, the pilot has been collaborating with:

- FabLab Spinderihallerne to iteratively create prototypes and bring solutions to a bigger scale while boosting economic growth and resilience.
- Den Gamle Gård: on tackling the very practical barrier for correct waste sorting – namely, how to fit bins for all 10 waste fractions in small kitchens and apartments.
- Collaboration with Sønnich Sønnichsen, Associated professor at the Copenhagen Business School, to give input to the public procurement policy in healthcare institutions in Vejle.

Outlined in the following section, is a rough collection of the different feedback activities the Vejle Pilot conducted in relation to the different test-sites and prototypes.

Sofiegården- mobile sorting unit: With the Sofiegården management and health personnel, interviews, observation, and a qualification workshop were conducted. The aim was to collect insights to everyday operations and qualification of ambitions and vision for future prototypes. This resulted in identifying challenges, needs and potentials resulting in vision for prototypes.

A co-creating workshop was also held with: fablab, entrepreneurs, SMVs, procurement department Municipality and Waste management to develop the physical prototype (mobile sorting unit). Feedback was aimed at CREOS design, the company who develops the physical prototype. The outcome was an iteration of the sorting unit with optimized functions. A business model for the mobile sorting unit was created in consultations with Copenhagen Business School.

Den Gamle Gård - From kitchen to yard: Similarly, to the work at Sofiegården, interviews, observations and a qualification workshop was conducted. Stakeholders included the board of Den Gamle Gård, consisting of residents, and a representative from the housing association (AAB) as well as other residents. Consequently, the Vejle pilot received insights to everyday life and operations, and input on the ambitions and vision for future prototypes. They identified challenges, needs and potentials resulting contributing to the pilot's vision for its prototypes.

Den Gamle Gård - Better sorting: Together with the FabLab, entrepreneurs, SMEs, procurement department Municipality and Waste management the Vejle Pilot held a co-creation workshop to collect of ideas for potential prototypes and their first take on prioritization. The workshop resulted in prototypes to develop further.

Figure 16: Photo at Spinderihallerne (Innovation Center, part of Vejle Municipality)

REMA 1000 - value chain game: Development meetings were held with Rema 1000 to identify what activities Rema 1000 and the Vejle Pilot could work on together. This resulted in a selection of activities to develop through Reflow. Further, a prototype development workshop was held in collaboration with The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, Aage Vestergaard Larsen, and Vejle Waste management to map the value chain of candy boxes. The workshop concluded on a qualified setup for how to develop the value chain game.

Figure 17: Workshop together with REMA 1000 and Danish Design Center

Validation

The Vejle pilot team qualitatively analysed the results and determined that there was 100% satisfaction for the new prototypes overall and across the test sites, as no participant expressed dissatisfaction with the functionality and their experiences with the solutions. See D1.5 – Project Impact Assessment, for more details.

- At Sofiegården, in relation to the scaling of the developed Mobile Sorting Unit, both employees and the manager expressed that there is a great desire to implement the waste solution in the other care centers in the Municipality
- In REMA 1000, the willingness to implement the solutions have been well-received. This is evident in the help that the Reflow Vejle pilot is providing REMA 1000 to introduce the same efforts in all their 350 stores in Denmark.
- At Den Gamle Gård, the willingness to test and implement the sorting bin solution was high for both the residents at the apartment block and the housing association, AAB. Moreover, the willingness to implement the solution has been realized through ABB's use of the solution in their new building on Nordholmen.

The Vejle Reflow project is being used as an exemplary project of citizen engagement in Vejle, which is a great validation of the quality of the pilot's work.

Regarding the work at Sofiegården, several healthcare institutions have expressed interest in the mobile sorting unit when the device is finalised. The procurement department in Vejle Municipality has also caught interest in the pilot's circular procurement methods and tools and have agreed to test and implement 2-3 of these tools in their tender agreements to stimulate demand on circularity.

Through a prototype development workshop, the Vejle pilot also sought to work out whether their solutions at REMA 1000 (value chain game) and Sofiegården (procurement policy), could work in different contexts. Vejle procurement department, the authority department, management, Sofiegården, Essity (supplier of diapers) and Vejle Waste management was invited to the session. The outcome of the workshop validated the fact that the value chain game works in different contexts (other than retailers), and that it can also help support the circular transition in relation to, for example, procurement in the municipality of Vejle. Further, a case about the value chain mapping game was published at the Knowledge Hub and local as well as international stakeholder published and reposted content about the pilots' actions on social media such as LinkedIn.

Last but not least, the sorting system created for Rema 1000 DK has been a huge success. From the pilot store, REMA 1000 in Skolegade in Vejle, the solution is now extended to all 360 stores across Denmark. Yearly, 600 tonnes of plastic from the retailer is now sent for recycling instead of incineration. The efforts of the Vejle pilot were recognised in a public announcement on social media, where REMA 1000 thanks the whole Vejle team consisting of the municipality, Danish Design Center (DDC) as well as close partners in REMA 1000. In short, the Vejle solution could not have received better validation for their hard work in the Reflow project over the past years.

8 Conclusion

In this deliverable, the Reflow projects interaction with its target audience both on a pilot and project level, has been described. Overarchingly, the deliverable shows that the project has been in close contact with externals, and that this has contributed both to gather feedback on project-and pilot level solutions, and that the Reflow solutions are largely validated and approved by both in the local and European context. The engagement has further contributed to the dissemination of the project and its mission, which is reflected in D7.3 Communication and Dissemination Activities Report.

In regards to the relation with the Covenant of Mayors and policy institutions, the interactions have been fewer than with the other target audiences for the project as a whole. Interaction has been attempted, and partially achieved, but not as close as originally anticipated. The close connection between pilot cities and their local public institutions can however be seen as a compensation for this. And perhaps establishing connections with policy makers on a local level is easier, and even more fruitful, than on a European level, given the organisational distance both between the units, and their connection to the topics in question.

For the other target audiences, especially the pilots have established and maintained strong bonds and ongoing interactions with local stakeholders in their fields. This has been important to ensure that the developed solutions have a chance to move up from the pilot stage at the end of the project, as they are somewhat already presented to the field. The WPs have also interacted actively with their respective fields and beyond, making sure that none of the solutions were developed in isolation, and have the potential to be used outside of the project. The work of interacting with externals by both pilots and WPs in addition contributes to the further exploitation of the project's outputs.

In general, the feedback has been constructive for all solutions, and led to important optimisations of the solutions. Further, all solutions have received validation in different shapes. From concrete commitments of implementation to presentations at various conferences to establishment of new partnerships. An important sign of validation of the Reflow project as a whole, is the recent launch of the European Commission's 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities scheme, where more than a hundred cities have committed to reach zero emissions by 2030. Of these, four are Reflow pilot cities (Amsterdam, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, and Paris). The pilots have stated that being part of Reflow was highlighted in their applications, and that it contributed to them being chosen. This signifies an overarching validation of the Reflow project.

In sum, the collaboration with external communities has been valuable for both pilots, WPs and the project as a whole, both in terms of fine-tuning the solutions, and preparing the ground for further development and exploitation.

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